

The Impact of Trading Technology Particularly Automation on Zimbabwe Stock Exchange (Zse) Performance

Author's Details:

(1)* Lucky Tuzuka Musikavanhu (2) Mufaro Andrew Matandare (3) Noel Zhou

^{1,2&3} Faculty of Commerce, BA ISAGO University, Gaborone, Botswana

P. Bag 149, Suite # 268, Kgale View Postnet, Gaborone, Botswana

^{1*} Corresponding author

Abstract

Automation of the Zimbabwe Securities Exchange was implemented in 2014 with the aim of improving the efficiency of stock market performance as measured by efficiency, turnover and market capitalization. The purpose of this study was to measure the impact of automation on the Zimbabwe stock exchange (ZSE) performance. Annual secondary data from 2012 to 2017 was used to measure the impact of automation on stock market performance. Panel vector autoregressive (PVAR) model was used on twelve firms to analyse the effect of automation on ZSE performance. The results indicated that the performance of the ZSE had been improved by the introduction of automation. The study recommends that ZSE should pursue full market automation as this will improve the performance of the stock market, especially in the long term

Keywords: Trading Technology, Stock Exchange, Zse

1. Introduction and background

The Stock exchange was first established in 1896 and became operational for six years in Bulawayo. Other stock markets in the small towns of Gweru and Mutare were shut down in 1924, and in 1946 it reopened again in Bulawayo. In 1951 the second floor was opened in Harare with trading done through telephones. The stock exchange was officially named the ZSE after independence, and it opened up for foreign investors in 1993, (Muzamani, 1993). The Zimbabwe Stock Exchange (ZSE) is licensed in terms of the Securities and Exchange Act (24:25) to assist companies to raise long term capital through the listing of securities as well as offer an investing platform through trading of listed securities, (Mpofu, 2011). Securities are defined in the Securities and Exchange Act (24:25) to mean shares, debt securities, depository receipts, futures and or contracts for differences, (Chirume, 2014).

Since 1896, trading has been manual where the system was paper based, and a trading record was published by the ZSE daily and circulated to stock broking firms and other firms. In 2014 the regulatory authorities passed a decision to automate the ZSE with the inclusion of the Central Depository Security (CDS) system which involves safer storage of securities and facilitate the transfer of securities through an automated book entry, (Jecheche, 2008). The Automated Trading System (ATS) had the advantages of Transparency in security trades and enhanced trade execution speed. Furthermore, ATS eliminates human interference and stockbrokers can do business from anywhere without attending "Call-Over" sessions at the ZSE which generates real time data that can be accessed by anyone with access rights to the system. Such information is vital to traders and investors in making investment decisions, (Mpofu, 2011).

Currently, there are 62 companies which are listed at the ZSE as at January 2017 and a market capitalization of \$2,936 billion from the 18 sectors of the economy which have improved as it has risen by 38, 4% and 54% in its value as compared to the values in 2012 where the stock exchange was still using the manual open outcry trading system. Trading now is done through the automated trading system as compared to the open outcry system which was done, (Pindula, 2017).

The impact of ATS on the ZSE stock market performance has not been studied extensively. Theoretically, automation improves the efficiency of the performance of the stock market. However, the impact of automation on different stock exchanges has yielded contradicting results. For instance, several studies revealed that the ATS had improved the performance of stock markets as measured by liquidity and market capitalization, (Levin, et al., 2002; Baker, 2005; Battalio, 2003 and Bias, 2005). Contrastingly, studies by Jain, (2005); Otukey, (2006) and Tendulkar, (2013) have concluded that ATS leads to market inefficiencies. Against this background,

it would be interesting to investigate the impact of ATS on the performance of ZSE focusing on efficiency, turnover and market capitalization.

2. Literature review

2.1 Theoretical literature

The automation and stock market exchange premise is based on the microstructure theory which determines the link between the organization of a particular securities market and market quality as defined by transactional and informational efficiency, liquidity, volatility. The theory is premised on the efficient market hypothesis, (Stoll, 2006). Market microstructure analyses the process in which investors' latent demands are translated into trading prices and volumes is central to the theory and sociology of investors' trading behavior, (Madhavan, 2000). Market microstructure studies expound on the critical areas of price formation, market structure and rules, transparency and regulatory structure, which entails the ability of market participants to observe information about the trading process and act on such information in an informed manner, (Shavelson, 2003).

Smith (2008) opines that the automated trading system is a system that handles trading operations or functions, including order routing, price setting, and trade execution. Tendulkar et al. (2013) supported the opinion that electronic trading systems are usually associated with electronic order routing and dissemination of trade information and may link through to clearing and settlement. In this case, automated trading systems are regarded as all systems and sub-systems used by the stock exchange to facilitate these functions which are order routing, dispersion of trading information and settlement. This can be initiated by the execution of Central Security Depository (CSD) system which is an automated electronic book entry system that is responsible for the entering and maintaining securities and transferring them to the other parties. Notably, the central depository system (CDS) is very crucial in facilitating the transfer of securities reducing the settlement days from more days to fewer days and reduction of systematic risk. The ATS has addressed the limitations of the manual trading in terms of the traded volumes handled and the speed at which transactions can be executed, (Smith, 2008).

ATS enables the market to operate at a lower cost and its ability to evaluate information and determine the fair value of a security, thus operational and informational efficiency respectively, (Levin et al. 2002). Moreover, ATS facilitates increased volumes of shares traded on the stock markets thus attributing to turnover and value of shares. Automation increases turnover due to the improved inter-broker settlement of transactions; reduced broker activity increased stock market operations as well as reduced fraud, (Jines, 2010). Mandelson (2009) concluded that ATS improves market capitalization which occurs due to fluctuations in share prices or issuance of new share prices or issuance of new shares and bonus issues. Improved market capitalization as a result of automation will make investors to be rewarded with a consistent increase in share value and dividend payments, (Asewe et al. 2010). Brailsford et al. (2000) emphasize that automated stock trading system offers greater transparency and dissemination in regard to the quotes and prices of securities. Automated stock trading system exhibit higher feedback on stock trading and provide greater lead time over returns on the securities traded.

2.2 Empirical literature

The issue of automating the stock markets has been met with mixed reactions as various scholars came up with contradicting results based on the exact effect of ATS on stock market performance. Several researchers found that automating the stock markets have improved the performance of stock markets.

For instance, the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) improved its capitalization after it was automated in 1999. Results showed that the investors' confidence, the volume of stock cleared and transparency of operations had been improved, and there has been an increase in the stock exchange's capitalization from N763.9 billion in 2002, N1.359 trillion in 2003, and N5.12 trillion in 2006, (Luka, 2011). The same results were further confirmed by Murinde (2006) in his research carried out on Nairobi Stock Exchange. The results indicated that average mean market returns in the automated period were higher and more volatile than those in the period where the stock exchange was in the process of moving from manual to electronic systems. These higher returns on the market were attributed to price discovery process, while the higher volatility may have been caused by changes in market microstructure through the trading system, implying that the market improved in efficiency, as was also noted by Okumu (2013).

Similarly, Muli (2008) employed observation and questionnaires method to assess the impact of Automation on the Ugandan Stock Exchange (USE). The results were that automated trading systems increased financial market efficiency, enhanced investor confidence, faster settlement of transactions through the CDS accounts, the transaction time and greater market returns settlement risk is checked. Hendershott (2011) noted an increase in liquidity, an improvement in efficiency and volume increase following the automation of the Singapore stock exchange (SSE).

On the other hand, Tendulkar (2013) found that the level of informational efficiency remains unchanged during the automation period of the Toronto Stock Exchange (TSE). Mensah and Poma (2012) found out that automation has led to the market inefficiency of the Ghana Stock Exchange (GSE) in a study carried out from 2006 to 2011. This had been largely attributed to the fact that firms were slow to respond to automation thus firms which were inefficient in the pre-automation period maintained their status even after the automation. The inflexible regulatory framework was among the reason for the market inefficiency after automation. Malkiel (2003) examined the effect of the automation of Amman Stock Exchange (ASE) on the market efficiency using the daily closing price index for a period of 10 years and found that the shift to electronic trading system increased volatility and had no significant effect on the market's efficiency. Similarly, electronic trading significantly influenced market liquidity and resulted in negative abnormal returns on the Amman Stock Exchange (ASE), (Harris, 2012). The automation of the Tunisian Stock Exchange (TSE) did not have a significant effect on efficiency, (Malkiel, 2007).

Thus as seen above, results of automation on stock market exchange brought mixed evidence. It would be of interest to analyze the impact of automation on the ZSE.

3. Research methodology

The study has employed a panel vector autoregressive (PVAR) model on a sample of 12 companies with dummies for the pre-automation period for a six year period from 2012 to 2017. This model combines the traditional vector autoregressive (VAR) approach with panel data. This approach improves on the ones employed in previous studies in that it increases the efficiency in analysis while capturing both co-existent and temporal relationships among variables, (Mishkin and Schmidt-Hebbel, 2007).

The Least Squares Dummy Variable (LSDV) Model was used to find out how stock exchange performance (Y) depends on the following independent variables: automation status (AS) and time since automation (TSA)

The regression model used is specified below:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AS + \beta_2 TSA + \mu_i \quad (1)$$

Where:

Y is the dependent variable indicators of stock market performance, i.e., Market capitalization (MK) and Stock turnover (ST),

β_0 is the constant regression coefficient,

β_1 and β_2 are the slopes of the regression equation,

μ_i is an error term normally distributed about a mean of 0, and for purposes of computation, the μ is assumed to be 0.

AS and TSA are the independent variables – Automation status and time since automation

4. Econometric test results

4.1 Stationarity test

The Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) was employed to examine the time series properties of the data as it removes all the structural effects (autocorrelation) in the time series and then tests using the same procedure as of the Dickey-Fuller Test. In statistics, a unit root test tests whether a time series variable is non-stationary using an autoregressive model.

Table 4.1: Summary of unit root test

Variables	ADF p-value level	ADF p-value first difference	Order of intergration	Level of stationarity
Market capital (MK)	0.5500	0.0000	1	**
Stock turnover (ST)	0.1071	0.0000	1	**
Time since auto (TSA)	1.0000	0.0000	1	**
Automation status (AS)	0.0910	0.0000	1	**

** means that data is stationary at first difference

The results indicate that the variables are stationary at first difference as shown by the p- value which is less than 5%

4.2 Multicollinearity

The correlation matrix was then used to test for Multicollinearity, where if the correlation coefficient between any two independent variables is $>.80$, one of the variables is dropped to avoid the problem of multicollinearity in the regression.

Table 4.2: Correlation matrix

	AS	MK	TSA	ST
AS	1	-0.0161	0.2472	-0.0879
MK	-0.0161	1	0.4045	-0.0799
TSA	0.2472	-0.0392	1	0.4341
ST	-0.0879	-0.0799	0.4342	1

Since all the coefficients are less than 80%, it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity.

4.3 Heteroscedasticity

The Breusch Pagan-Godfrey test was used to test for heteroscedasticity

Table 4.3: Heteroskedastity test

Heteroscedasticity Test :Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey				
F-statistic		3.1843		Prob.F(6,11) 0.046
obs*R-squared		6.3633		Prob.Chi-Square.(6) 0.0117
ScaLed explained SS		56127		Prob.Chi-Square.(6) 0.4679

A heteroskedasticity test was performed to check if variances of error terms are homoscedastic. The test looks at the corresponding P-value of Obs*R-squared as a measurement. An Obs*R –square test statistic of 6.36 was obtained with p- value of 0.0117. At 5 % significance level, the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis that there is a constant variance and hence there is no evidence of heteroscedasticity.

4.4 Auto-Correlation

The Breusch-Godfrey Serial/Auto Correlation was used to check if there existed a serial correlation between the dependent and independent variables followed by Durbin Watson (DW) test.

Table 4.4: Serial correlation test

Breusch-Godfrey-Serial Correlation LM Test				
F-statistic		0.0301	Prob. F(1,10)	0.8656
Obs*R-squared		0.0541	Prob. Chi-Square(1)	0.8161

The results exhibit no serial correlation among the residuals since the probability of chi-square (0.8161) is more than 0.05. Evidence from the above diagnostic test reveals the suitability of the model in reducing the effect of automation on market capitalization and stock turnover.

4.5 Fixed/ Random effect

Hausman test was used to determine the suitable model to be used. The results as indicated below shows that the P- value is less than 5% thus concluding the appropriateness of the fixed effect.

Table 4.5: Hausman Test Result for fixed or random effect

Test Summary			
	Chi-Sq.Statistics	Chi-Sq.d.f	Prob
Gross-section random	4.939222	4	0.236

4.6 Least Squares Dummy Variable (LSDV) regression output

From the literature, review arguments are that automation has a significant positive impact on stock market performance as measured by either market capitalization or stock turnover. To analyze this, the researcher used the least squares dummy variable regression model to analyses the effect of trading technology on ZSE.

4.6.1 Market capitalization regression output

Table 4.6 presents the output of the regression of market capitalization (MK) on time since automation (TSA) and automation status (AS).

From table 4.6, Sig F < 0.05 indicating that the model applied is consistent and fits well with the objectives of the study. The joint parameters have a significant relationship with the dependent variable. The regression equation shows that the independent variable like time since automation (TSA), impact positively on the performance of the stock market based on the market capitalization. The relationship is however weak since the R square is only 0.21 or 21%. The P-value < 0.05 for all independent variables under study. Automation status has a negative impact on the performance of securities exchanges. This analysis indicates that the impact of automation on stock market performance may not be immediate but may be felt over time as the exchange embrace advances in trading technology.

This is because automation reduces transaction costs, by expediting the execution of orders to buy and sell securities, by expediting the reporting of executions to investors, and by accommodating a greater number of participants than is possible in a traditional trading system, (Baker et al. 2004). The findings of this paper confirm findings by Otchere and Hazarika (2009) on the positive effects of automation on stock market capitalization.

Table 4.6: Market Capitalization Regression Output

Regression Statistics								
Multiple R	0.46							
R Square	0.21							
Adjusted R Square	0.20							
Standard Error	822.38							
Observations	600							
ANOVA								
	<i>Df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>			
Regression	6	107,721,737.04	17,953,622.84	26.55	0.00			
Residual	593	401,054,346.35	676,314.24					
Total	599	508,776,083.40						
	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	32.22	69.66	0.46	0.64	(104.58)	169.03	(104.58)	169.03
AS	(329.80)	110.24	(2.99)	0.00	(546.32)	(113.29)	(546.32)	(113.29)
TSA	32.02	9.06	3.53	0.00	14.22	49.81	14.22	49.81

MK = 32.22+ 32.02TSA– 329.80AS

4.6.2 Stock Turnover Regression Output

Table 4.7 below presents the output of the regression of stock turnover (ST) on time since automation (TSA) and automation status (AS).

Table 4.7: Multiple Regression Output for Stock Turnovers

Regression Statistics								
Multiple R	0.53							
R Square	0.28							
Adjusted R Square	0.27							
Standard Error	69.44							
Observations	600							
ANOVA								
	Df	SS	MS	F	Significance F			
Regression	6	1,117,321.88	186,220.31	38.62	0.00			
Residual	593	2,859,143.19	4,821.49					
Total	599	3,976,465.07						
	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	1.36	5.88	0.23	0.82	(10.20)	12.91	(10.20)	12.91
AS	(17.43)	9.31	(1.87)	0.06	(35.71)	0.85	(35.71)	0.85
TSA	2.88	0.77	3.77	0.00	1.38	4.38	1.38	4.38

ST = 1.36 + 2.88TSA – 17.43AS

Since $F < 0.05$ it implies that the model properly fit the research design. The independent variables have a significant joint relationship with the dependent variable stock turnover. However, R square is only 0.28 or 28% which signifies a weak relationship. The regression model shows that time since automation, have a positive impact on the value of shares traded. However, it is only the p-value of TSA that are less than 0.05 indicating that indeed there is a significantly positive relationship between the values of shares traded. These results are supported by Freud and Pagan (2000) who pointed out that the improvement in market capitalization and stock turnover exchange performance cannot only be attributed to automation.

5. Conclusions and recommendations

Market capitalization and stock turnover tend to increase over time following automation. This study concludes that over a period of time, automation improves market capitalization and stock turnover. This conclusion, however, contradicts the findings of various authors. For example, Otchere, et al. (2008) showed that automation improves stock exchange performance regardless of time.

Generally, automation reduces the costs and inefficiencies associated with manual systems and increases trading activity and liquidity in the stock market by speeding up operations. The research, therefore, concludes that automation is value enhancing. This conclusion confirms the results of earlier studies on the impact of automation on stock turnover, (Madhavan, 2002). In line with arguments put forward by Theissen (2005) the researcher believes this is a consequence of competitive pressures. The research thus further concludes that automation is volume enhancing hence increase market turnover.

From the results of this paper, the following recommendations have been made:

- To consider pursuing full market automation of the market through the adoption of both online and internet securities trading. Through these, investors would not have to travel where the brokers have offices to trade in securities, but can rather log into the online trading platforms operated by brokers wherever they are and be able to access the electronic order book within the ATS of the ZSE.
- To adopt a hybrid trading system with both call and continuous system as was done at the Tunisian Stock Exchange and the NYSE. Both call and continuous systems have been found to be effective on thinly traded stocks and heavily traded stocks respectively, (Hendershott and Moulton, 2011).
- There is a need for the Securities Commissions of Zimbabwe (SECZ) to set flexible laws that encourages business under an automated system and being able to sustain it.

- To launch a mobile application where ZSE should work with the ICT industry practitioners in order to harness the benefits of mobile telephones so that the thriving mobile money financial framework can mesh with the broker payment systems together with ATS and CDS in order to enable the securities buying, selling and making payments for such transactions through mobile money transfer system such as Eco cash, One Money, Telecash. The end result will increase in market activity, enhanced liquidity and transparency, and heightened investor confidence, thus leading to improvement in securities market efficiency.

The drawback of this study is the inclusion of only two independent variables (TSA and AS). This could result in the problem of omission of other important variables. Therefore, other future studies can include other variables like age, time since demutualization, economic status and demutualization status. The difficulty with the empirical comparison is that different markets operate in different environments. Hence, it is difficult to separate the effects resulting from the change in the trading mechanism itself from those due to differences in institutional environments. The common findings pointed out in all empirical studies on automation is the improvement of liquidity, which is often sought by emerging markets but no unanimous conclusion is noted on other market characteristics. Thus this study recommends other future studies to also analyze the effects of institutional variables on the stock market exchange.

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